

COMBINING ABILITY ESTIMATES FROM LINE X TESTER MATING DESIGN IN UPLAND COTTON

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Abstract:

Combining ability estimates and variances are essential genetic parameters to cotton researchers in gaining improvement via hybridization and selection programmes. The current Line x tester evaluation programme involving five female lines and eight testers, was experimented at three different locations to exploit the four yield related traits and earliness index in upland cotton. The importance of GCA and SCA variances was evident from mean squares of all the five traits showing that additive as well as non-additive genes controlled the traits. However, among the five female lines, NH 615 showed maximum GCA effects for number of bolls (1.562) earliness index (0.008), while female line AKH 081 was found best general combiner for boll weight (0.126) and lint yield (4.524). Whereas for seed cotton yield, female line AK 32 (12.172) recorded as a best general combiner. The next high GCA scoring parent for seed cotton yield (11.358) was AKH 081. Among the testers, parent AKH 09-5 was promising, as manifested highest estimates of GCA effects for seed cotton yield (11.506) and lint yield (3.450). While, parents Suraj, PH 10-60 and AKH 10-10 were evolved as best general combiners for number of bolls (3.609), boll weight (0.20) and earliness index (0.012) respectively. The GCA estimates as a whole suggested that if most of the traits are to be improved through hybridization and selection, then priority should be given to parents AKH 09-5, Suraj, PH 10-60 and AKH 10-10 from among the testers and NH 615, AKH 081 and AK 32 from among the female lines. The hybrid NH 615 x CNH 83-1 exhibited maximum SCA effect for number of bolls per plant; AK 32 x AKH 10-10 for boll weight; AK 32 x SURAJ for seed cotton yield and lint yield. While the hybrid NH 545 x AKH 13-01 recorded highest SCA effect for earliness index.

Keywords: line x tester analysis, combining ability estimates, earliness, upland cotton

Introduction

To select appropriate and diverse parents is the first step for successful breeding programme and it is one of the most important criteria used to find the most promising hybrids and increase the efficiency of breeding programme. Identification of better parents is done on the basis of general combining ability and the selected parents are used in further crop improvement programme. Selection of superior crosses is performed on the basis of specific combining ability effects. Allard, 1960 pointed out that the general approach of selecting the parents on the basis of *per se* performance is not good identification of their superior combining ability. The choice of parents in any breeding programme has to be based on complete genetic information and knowledge of combining ability of the parents and not merely on the field performance of different genotypes.

General combining ability is due to genes which are largely additive in their effects and specific combining ability is due to the genes with dominance or epistatic effect, according to Sprague and Tatum, 1942.

Thus, considering the importance of combining ability of the parents for various plant characters in cotton, the line x tester analysis was carried out. The estimates of various genetic parameters would provide guidelines to the cotton breeders to launch effective breeding strategies.

Materials and Methods

The experimental treatments consist of 40 F₁s generated from line x tester mating design by crossing 5 lines and 8 testers (5 lines *viz.* AK 32, AKH 081, NH 615, PHULE 688 and NH 545 and 8 testers AKH 09-5, AKH 10-3, AKH 10-10, AKH 13-01, PH 10-60, RHC 12-17, CNH 83-1 and SURAJ) along with two checks (PKV Hy 2 and AKH 9916) were evaluated over 3 environments *viz.*, Akola (E1), Buldana (E2) and Amravati (E3) of Maharashtra state, India, during *kharif* season 2018-19. The experiment was laid-out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications.

Five random selected plants were tagged from each replication for recording data. All the cultural practices like irrigation and fertilizer were applied as per recommendations whenever needed. The data were recorded for 18 agronomic characters over the three environments. Bartlett's (1973), Index was used to measure earliness index as per Chang (2001). The mean squares from line x tester analysis and the

general combining ability (GCA) along with specific combining (SCA) variances and effects were calculated according to the procedures developed by Kempthorne, 1957 and adopted by Singh and Choudhry, 1979.

Results and Discussion:

Based on pooled analysis for combining ability, the variance due to environments x crosses interaction was found to be significant for most of the characters; indicating desirable amount of interaction between the hybrids and environments. Mean sum of squares due to males x females interaction were significant for all the characters under study except for days to 50 % flowering, days to 50 % boll bursting, boll weight, seed index, elongation percentage and earliness index, which indicated adequate genetic variability among the crosses for specific combining ability. Environments x males x females interaction was also found to be significant for some important traits, which indicated considerable variability for specific combining ability among the crosses to the environments for these traits (Table 1).

Two parents *viz.*, AK 32 and AKH 081 were found to be the best general combiners along with high mean performance for seed cotton yield and other yield contributing traits. While parent AKH 09-5 exhibited high mean performance for seed cotton yield (89.56 g) with highly significant gca effect for seed cotton yield per plant, days to 50 % flowering, days to 50 % boll bursting, number of monopodia, lint yield, and fibre fineness. Whereas, the parent AKH 10-10 which evolved as good combiner for earliness index (0.012) along with other traits. Similarly, parent SURAJ though does not exhibit significant gca effect for seed cotton yield but recorded promising significant gca effects for number of sympodia per plant (1.68), number of bolls per plant (3.60) and elongation percentage (0.067) along with desired high mean *per se* performance for the traits *viz.*, days to 50 % flowering, days to 50 % boll bursting, number of monopodia per plant, boll weight, seed index, lint index, ginning percentage and earliness index, (Tale, 2).

Based on high mean performance, significantly high sca effects and significant heterosis over standard check, six promising hybrids *viz.*, AK 32 x SURAJ, AK 32 x AKH 09-5, AKH 081 x AKH 09-5, AKH 081 x SURAJ, AKH 081 x AKH 10-10, and NH 615 x AKH 09-5 were selected for seed cotton yield over the three test environments.

The hybrid, AK 32 x SURAJ, including good x poor general combiner parents for seed cotton yield, recorded highest *per se* performance (119.41 g); exhibited highest and significant sca effects for seed cotton yield per plant (13.469) with significant sca effects for other yield contributing and fibre quality traits in desirable direction. This cross AK 32 x SURAJ had good x poor combining parents. Positive and significant sca effects in crosses between good and poor combiners could be ascribed to better complementation between favorable alleles of the parents involved. Consequently, this hybrid appeared promising for commercial release after thorough testing.

Whereas, the hybrid AKH 081 x AKH 09-5 (good x good general combiner parents for seed cotton yield); having high *per se* for seed cotton yield (110.40 g) though does not showed significant sca effects for seed cotton yield, but, exhibited desired sca effects for other traits *viz.*, days to 50 % flowering, days to 50 % boll bursting, plant height, number of monopodia per plant, number of sympodia per plant, number of bolls per plant, seed index, fibre strength and elongation percentage. Further, cross combination AKH 081 x SURAJ, recorded high *per se* for seed cotton yield (110.33 g) exhibited, significant sca effects for boll weight, lint index, lint yield and ginning percentage with non-significant sca effects for seed cotton yield and involves, good x poor general combiner parents for seed cotton yield, in the cross.

The hybrid, AKH 081 x AKH 10-10 with higher *per se* performance (107.16 g) had also showed significant sca effects for number of sympodia per plant, lint index, fibre strength and uniformity index; with non-significant sca effects for seed cotton yield and involves good x poor general combiner parents for seed cotton yield in the cross. Similarly, cross combination AK 32 x AKH 09-5 (105.53 g *per se*); with highly significant, standard heterosis and mean for seed cotton yield, though showed non-significant sca effects for seed cotton yield involves good x good general combiner parents for seed cotton yield. This cross though exhibited non-significant sca effects for seed cotton yield, but recorded significant sca effects for days to 50 % boll bursting coupled with earliness index in desirable direction. The hybrids *viz.* AK 32 x AKH 09-5, AKH 081 x AKH 09-5, NH 615 x AKH 09-5 displayed non-significant specific combining ability effects for seed cotton yield per plant, lint yield per plant and days to 50 % flowering. Similar situation was also noticed in AKH 081 x SURAJ, NH 615 x AKH 09-5 and PHULE 688 x SURAJ for number of bolls per plant; AK 32 x AKH 09-5, AK 32 x AKH 10-10 and PHULE 688 x AKH 09-5 for the trait fibre fineness; NH 615 x AKH 10-10 for earliness index. However, all these hybrids were found to involve both the parents with good general combining ability for the concerning traits, Table 3.

Similarly, one cross combination AK 32 x AKH 09-5 and NH 545 x AKH 13-01 from above mentioned six hybrids had also recorded high *per se* performance for seed cotton yield; thus these hybrids could be advanced and exploited in further generations to obtain promising transgressive segregants having early maturity coupled with high yield. The cross combinations having high mean yield and desirable sca effects is of immense importance for hybrid cotton breeding programme. With highest record of *per se* performance (119.41), the cross AK 32 x SURAJ also showed higher F_1 *per se* performance coupled with positive and significant sca effects for most of the yield contributing traits, also Out of these six cross combinations, AK 32 revealed as best general combiner for seed cotton yield (12.178) amongst all parents and plays a vital role to form outperforming heterotic crosses. All these crosses had good x poor combining parents, which indicates non-additive gene action and open an avenue to exploit the available vigour through heterosis breeding. Patel and Mehta (1985), Gururajan and Basu (1992), Rao and Reddy (2002) and Saini *et al.* (2005) also stressed the importance of good x poor crosses in obtaining superior combinations.

For earliness index, the cross combinations, NH 545 x AKH 13-01 (9.93) followed by NH 545 x RHC 12-17 (9.21) had exhibited highest significant values and high *per se* performance (0.73; 0.72). Both the crosses had positive significant sca effects with poor x poor combiners. Whereas, the cross combination, AKH 081 x AKH 10-10 recorded high *per se* performance (0.73) for earliness index. This cross has involvement of poor x good general combiner with positive sca effects. Thus, positive sca effects in cross between poor x good general combiner could be credited to better complementation between favorable alleles of the parents involved in the cross.

Similarly, with highest *per se* performance (0.73) and having involvement of both good general combiners, the cross, NH-615 x AKH-10-10 exhibited positive sca effects. The parent AKH 10-10 was revealed as best general combiner amongst all the parents, for the trait earliness index. As the cross had both combining parents for earliness index, the heterosis in this cross might have resulted from interaction of dominant gene contributed by both good combining parents. Pathak and Kumar (1975) reported close relationship between gca effects of parents and heterotic effects of their resultant crosses.

Conclusions and recommendations

Four parents *viz.*, AK 32, AKH 081, AKH 09-5 and SURAJ exhibited high mean performance and with highly significant gca effect for seed cotton yield can be used in recombination breeding to obtain more favorable gene recombination for seed cotton yield and also for improvement of yield and associated characters along with earliness index.

This study also revealed that, the parents possessing high x high or high x low gca effects do not necessarily produce hybrids with high sca effects.

Thus, it could be concluded that, hybrids showing high sca effects for seed cotton yield and other important traits were having at least one parent with high gca effects. The performance of cross combinations, are therefore largely in agreement with the gca effects of parents involved in the combinations.

The highest *per se* and significant sca effect for seed cotton yield per plant obtained by the hybrid AK 32 x SURAJ is a clear indication of the presence of dominance gene action and this hybrid is highly suitable for heterosis breeding to fully exploit the dominance gene action and to improve the yield and other quality traits.

Further, the hybrids AKH 081 x AKH 09-5, AK 32 x AKH 09-5 and NH 615 x AKH 09-5 could be recommended for recombination breeding as they satisfied for important yield, yield components and fibre quality traits. As the recombination breeding procedures allow further combination of alleles in segregating generations, so that we could obtain genotypes with favorable combination of alleles for the traits under genetic improvement.

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Table 1: Pooled analysis of variance for combining ability over the three environments

Sources of variation	d.f.	Mean sum of squares								
		Days to 50% flowering	Days to 50% boll bursting	Plant height	Number of monopodia per plant	Number of sympodia per plant	Number of bolls per plant	Boll weight	Seed index	Lint index
Environments	2	1.91731**	1.39061**	135.5967**	0.00716**	1.88677	5.89335**	0.06053	0.28122	0.35701
Crosses	39	58.46636	302.4531	810.2579**	0.76332**	46.85252**	258.5415**	0.60197	1.60821*	2.59151**
Females	4	433.9702	1533.868	915.9401**	1.42984**	77.56695**	357.3298**	0.83034	2.99286*	4.85798**
Males	7	22.29891	150.9792	580.7731**	0.61545**	37.09702**	130.3177**	0.88297	2.38615*	3.98908**
Males x females	28	13.86482	164.405	852.5317**	0.70507**	44.90362**	276.4848**	0.49909	1.21592	1.91833**
Environments x crosses	78	2.11255	4.14903	27.2008**	0.02829**	0.3208	1.29225	0.03203	0.16926	0.25407
Environments x females	8	1.98679*	3.66133	40.89808**	0.03017**	0.15796	1.0736	0.0194	0.08206	0.12044
Environments x males	14	1.27985**	4.81768	12.70049**	0.03647**	0.38896	2.41735**	0.02642	0.28804	0.43887
Environments x males x females	56	2.33869	4.05154	28.86913**	0.02597**	0.32703	1.04221	0.03523	0.15202	0.22696
Error	312	7.39187	24.20913	9.92712	0.022	1.13412	9.57663	0.04739	0.28776	0.1428

Sources of variation	d.f.	Mean sum of squares								
		Seed cotton yield/ plant	Lint yield/ plant	Ginning percentage	UHML	Fibre strength	Fibre fineness	Uniformity index	Elongation percentage	Earliness index
Environments	2	1364.218**	179.8164**	2.6135	0.82617	0.89874	0.06129**	5.56794**	0.01079	0.05647
Crosses	39	2090.284**	298.7018**	14.299**	14.43071**	20.00478**	0.76193**	3.2407**	0.07476	0.00318
Females	4	14291.37**	2011.729**	26.00137**	29.86593**	20.60745**	2.05973**	6.54938**	0.10353	0.00174
Males	7	1442.496**	165.7722**	21.22034**	21.19658**	17.93287**	0.42037**	3.33279**	0.10000	0.00268
Males x females	28	509.2196**	87.21592**	10.89689**	10.53421**	20.43666**	0.66192**	2.74501**	0.06434	0.00351
Environments x crosses	78	154.6405**	25.0844**	1.52223**	0.24447	0.16134	0.07408**	2.2608**	0.06438	0.0008
Environments x females	8	672.8969**	93.62422**	0.79281	0.11991	0.30326	0.05628**	6.48377**	0.16425	0.00103
Environments x males	14	60.12605**	13.15638**	2.55254**	0.30169	0.15495	0.08773**	1.49161	0.06913	0.00078
Environments x males x females	56	104.2324**	18.275**	1.36885	0.24796	0.14267	0.07321**	1.84982**	0.04893	0.00077
Error	312	228.7825	32.41536	0.92177	2.00037	3.72658	0.10844	1.36145	0.00244	0.00086

*, ** - significant at 5 % and 1 % level, respectively

Table 2: Table 4.12: GCA effects of promising parents in desirable direction for seed cotton yield, its related traits and fibre properties over the environments

Sr. No.	Genotypes	Days to 50% flowering	Days to 50% boll bursting	Plant height	Number of monopodia per plant	Number of sympodia per plant	Number of bolls per plant	Boll weight	Seed index	Lint index
Females										
1	AK 32	-1.783**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	AKH 081	-	-3.726**	6.214**	-0.238**	0.849**	1.473**	0.126**	0.067	-
3	NH 615	-1.832**	-3.886**	-	-	-	1.562**	0.056*	0.258**	0.318**
4	PHULE 688	-	-	-	-	0.879**	1.184**	-	-	-
5	NH 545	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Males										
1	AKH 09-5	-1.015 **	-2.497**	-	-0.105 **	-	-	-	-	-
2	AKH 10-3	-	-	4.866**	-0.148 **	-	-	-	-	-
3	AKH 10-10	-	-1.671*	-	-	0.746 **	-	-	0.460**	0.612 **
4	AKH 13-01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5	PH 10-60	-	-	3.370**	-	-	-	0.200**	-	-
6	RHC 12-17	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.189**	0.170*	0.208 **
7	CNH 83-1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8	SURAJ	-	-	-	-	1.686 **	3.609 ***	-	-	-

Sr. No.	Genotypes	Seed cotton yield per plant	Lint yield per plant	Ginning percentage	UHML	Fibre strength	Fibre fineness	Uniformity index	Elongation percentage	Earliness index
Females										
1	AK 32	12.178**	3.795**	-	-	-	-0.124**	-	-	-
2	AKH 081	11.358**	4.524**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	NH 615	-	-	0.75**	-	0.672**	-	-	0.017**	0.008 *
4	PHULE 688	-	-	-	0.416*	0.339*	-0.191 **	-	-	-
5	NH 545	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.347*	0.022**	-
Males										
1	AKH 09-5	11.506**	3.450**	-	0.470*	-	-0.120 **	-	-	-
2	AKH 10-3	-	-	-	0.796**	0.600**	-	-	0.034**	-
3	AKH 10-10	-	-	1.385**	-	-	-0.107 **	-	-	0.012 **
4	AKH 13-01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5	PH 10-60	-	-	-	0.815**	0.481*	-	-	-	-
6	RHC 12-17	-	-	0.469**	-	-	-	-	0.031 **	-
7	CNH 83-1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8	SURAJ	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.067 **	-

*, ** - significant at 5 % and 1 % level, respectively

Table 3: Mean yield performance, standard heterosis (H₃) and SCA effects of the promising crosses over the environments

SN	Crosses	Seed cotton yield per plant (g)	Standard heterosis (H ₃) for seed cotton yield (%)		SCA effects for seed cotton yield /plant	GCA effects of parents for seed cotton yield	Significant SCA effects for other characters in desirable direction
			Check 1	Check 2			
1	AK 32 x SURAJ	119.41**	85.40**	114.38**	13.469*	12.178** x 4.566	3,4,5,6,10,11,15
2	AKH 081 x AKH 09-5	110.40**	71.41**	98.19**	-1.665	11.358** x 11.506**	1,2,3,4,5,6,8,14,17
3	AKH 081 x SURAJ	110.33**	71.30**	98.07**	5.207	11.358** x 4.566	7,9,11,12
4	AKH 081 x AKH 10-10	107.16**	66.38**	92.38**	6.701	11.358** x -0.101	5,6,14,16
5	AK 32 x AKH 09-5	105.53**	63.84**	89.45**	-7.356	12.178** x 11.506**	2,18
6	NH 615 x AKH 09-5	105.38**	63.62**	89.19**	-0.667	5.344** x 11.506**	3,4,14,17

1	Days to 50% Flowering	5	Number of Sympodia/ Plant	9	Lint Index (g)	13	UHML (mm)
2	Days to 50% Boll Bursting	6	Number of Bolls/plants	10	Seed Cotton yield/Plant (g)	14	Fibre Strength (g/tex)
3	Plant Height(cm)	7	Boll Weight(g)	11	Lint yield/Plant (g)	15	Fibre Fineness (µg/inch)
4	Number of Monopodia/Plant	8	Seed Index (g)	12	Ginning percentage	16	Uniformity Index (%)
17	Elongation percentage	18	Earliness Index				